

ARTICLES

THE PLAYERS IN THE NEW ENERGY SYSTEM: WHAT ROLE FOR THE STATE IN THE ANTHROPOCENE ERA?

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Energy is necessary for daily survival. Future development crucially depends on its long-term availability in increasing quantities from sources that are dependable, safe, and environmentally sound. At present, no single source or mix of sources is at hand to meet this future need.¹

INTRODUCTION

Energy is an essential good that provides the most primary services for human life.² The common future of mankind rests on a steady availability of energy from various sources.³ However, the current energy mix is overwhelmingly

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¹ WORLD COMMISSION ON ENVIRONMENT AND DEVELOPMENT, OUR COMMON FUTURE 168 (Oxford University Press, 1987).

² *Id.*

³ VAACLAV SMIL, ENERGY: A BEGINNER’S GUIDE 127 (Oneworld Publications, 2006).

composed of non-renewable energy,⁴ which requires a paradigm shift in order to meet humanity's future needs⁵ and to achieve energy efficiency.⁶ Hence, within two centuries—suffice it to say—all countries became dependent on fossil fuels.⁷ By virtue of a long-standing colonial legacy, African states have ironically entered the “fossil fuel civilization.”⁸ As a result, they claimed their right to development, joined the peloton of the industrial civilization—⁹at their own pace and steady effort—and chased the promise of development. In this sense, they disregarded their initial natural harmony and waded in a constraining, destructive and self-defeating venture.¹⁰ Above all, they have still had to bear disproportionately the double burden of the social and economic impacts of the Industrial Revolution over time.¹¹ To their detriment, they have also been subjected to a persistent environmental

⁴ VACLAV SMIL, *ENERGY AND CIVILIZATION: A HISTORY* 295 (The MIT Press, 2017) (affirming the current share “2015” of fossil fuels (86%) in global primary energy, which is only 4% less than a generation ago “1990”).

⁵ UN ENVIRONMENT (ed.), *GLOBAL ENVIRONMENT OUTLOOK – GEO-6: HEALTHY PLANET, HEALTHY PEOPLE* 9-10 (Cambridge University Press, 2019).

⁶ Renewable Energy Policy Network for the 21st Century [REN21], *Renewables 2018: Global Status Report*, at 165 (2018).

⁷ VACLAV SMIL, *supra* note 3, at 295-296.

⁸ *Id.* at 228.

⁹ VACLAV SMIL, *THE EARTH'S BIOSPHERE: EVOLUTION, DYNAMICS, AND CHANGE* 231 (The MIT Press, 2002).

¹⁰ LAVANYA RAJAMANI & JACQUELINE PEEL (eds.), *THE OXFORD HANDBOOK OF INTERNATIONAL ENVIRONMENTAL LAW* 1 (Oxford University Press, 2ed. 2021).

¹¹ A legitimate question that arises today is: was the industrial revolution necessary? Economists have been focusing on new questions, exploring new aspects based on new data to challenge conventional wisdom. *E.g.* GRAEME DONALD SNOOKS, *WAS THE INDUSTRIAL REVOLUTION NECESSARY?* (Routledge, 3ed. 2002).

and climate ordeal.

These challenges are so enormous for African states that they require a timely action. Earlier this decade, over half of the African people was without access to energy services. That is, nearly 590 million Africans (57% of the population) could not afford or lived in off-grid areas.¹² A sharp increase is observed when access to clean cooking fuels and cooking technologies is added to this figure, augmenting in the vicinity of 700 million people (68% of the population).¹³ It dawns upon everyone—with an unambivalent conclusiveness—that Africa is a widely diverse continent. Such diversity translates into varying levels of development between states, including the specific place of the energy sector in the national economic landscape. Thereby, fossil fuels and renewable energies are not equally incorporated into energy policies, which arguably leads to unequal access to energy services and soars the energy poverty. Consequently, this situation necessarily impacts—over the course of time—the overall productive activity and the access and consumption of communities and households. This is in fact the challenge that lies ahead for the new energy system when it comes to African states.¹⁴

Without a sudden fright, the state has a primary and fundamental role to play here.¹⁵ It entertains no doubt that major decisions must be taken to transform the energy mix,

¹² IRENA, *AFRICA'S RENEWABLE FUTURE: THE PATHWAY TO SUSTAINABLE GROWTH 5* (2013).

¹³ *Id.*

¹⁴ Gilbert Nzobadila, *Energy Poverty in Africa*, AFRICAN ENERGY COMMISSION (2017), https://au-afrec.org/Docs/FR/PDF/2017/paper_on_africa_energy_poverty_en.pdf

¹⁵ Tracy-Lynn Field, *A Just Energy Transition and Functional Federalism: The Case of South Africa* 10 *TRANSNATIONAL ENVIRONMENTAL LAW* 237, 237 (2021).

by increasing the share of renewable energies, alongside other socio-economic issues that need to be addressed.¹⁶ Domestic consumption is proving to be a genuine intersectional issue,¹⁷ including access to energy services, economic and energy poverty, energy efficiency and conservation, and other social challenges.¹⁸ Although renewable energy can make a considerable contribution to the energy mix, the state must actually reduce the share of energy resources usually exported to meet domestic needs. The changing environment of African states appears relatively challenging.¹⁹

Through this framework, I examine the role of African states in the context of the global change represented by the energy transition. Focusing on French-, Portuguese- and English-speaking states allows me to cross-reference three different legal traditions, but also to take a broader look at the conceptual meaning and materiality of the transition emerging from these different states. Most of these countries have historically experienced failed social experiments by various actors, including governments, non-state actors, and international organizations, on economic, social, and environmental issues.

Although the terminology tends to evolve nowadays, not so long ago they were literally considered “undeveloped countries.”²⁰ A conceptual approach that only finds real meaning in economic studies.²¹ One could argue *ab initio*

¹⁶ *Id.* at 238.

¹⁷ Thijs Etty et al., *Energy Transition in a Transnational World*, 10 *TRANSNATIONAL ENVIRONMENTAL LAW* 197, 199 (2021).

¹⁸ *Id.*

¹⁹ Johannes Saurer & Jonas Monast, *The Law of Energy Transition in Federal Systems*, 10 *TRANSNATIONAL ENVIRONMENTAL LAW*, 205, 205 (2021).

²⁰ E. WAYNE NAFZIGER, *ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT* 21 (Cambridge University Press, 4ed. 2006).

²¹ *Id.* at 02.

that the concept of development per se is problematic.²² It is certainly a by-product of biological studies that has been arbitrarily applied to the trajectory of social and economic progress of states in recent years. Most of them are in three different regions (Africa, Asia, and Latin America), facing different social and economic problems. Historically, they bear the burden of a disproportionate distribution of power and wealth,²³ resulting from industrial and economic domination.²⁴

However, one should be legitimate to ask: how come those underdeveloped countries could aspire to or achieve sustainable development? Could a country sustain its development while it is not developed? Can underdeveloped countries pretend to achieve sustainable development? Can sustainable development be a crossroads where developed and non-developed countries meet without any discrimination? Is sustainable development becoming the only mode of development? Does it definitively replace economic development, in the sense that achieving sustainable development means no longer going through the economic trajectory?²⁵

To date, it is hard to find a solid answer to those mere questions. Yet, there are still about 50 million indigenous people in Africa,²⁶ who live in great harmony with nature,

²² *Id.* at 21.

²³ ANTHONY SHORROCKS AND ROLPH VAN DER HOEVEN eds., *GROWTH, INEQUALITY, AND POVERTY PROSPECTS FOR PRO-POOR ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT* 144 (Oxford University Press, 2004) (analyzing the conditions for redistribution of growth between different areas).

²⁴ *Id.* at 02.

²⁵ KARL GUNNAR PERSSON, *AN ECONOMIC HISTORY OF EUROPE: KNOWLEDGE, INSTITUTIONS AND GROWTH, 600 TO THE PRESENT* 21 (Cambridge University Press, 4ed. 2010).

²⁶ See the International Work Group on Indigenous Affairs, at <http://www.iwgia.org/regions/africa>

passing on ancestral knowledge from generation to generation, and—for the most part—exploiting resources and lands very rationally. The Congo Basin and the Niger Delta epitomize the large areas that are currently home to many groups. When it comes to preserving lands and natural resources, their practices and lifestyle have proven to be effective. Anyone who has had the privilege of accessing their living environment could testify to this very fact. Is their way of life sustainable enough to be preserved for our common good? Should we continue to jeopardize their living environment in the name of economic growth driven by mining, expropriation, and deforestation?²⁷

As one can see, they bear a double burden. First, the burden of a disharmonious way of life that has led to a global catastrophe on nature and the ecosystem. As a result, the energy transition will impose an appalling social and environmental plight on them. Secondly, the burden of the promise of economic development²⁸ that always benefits a small group, while the indigenous people—and part of the people—endure the hardship. Not to mention the imperiousness of those who plausibly claim to bring them sustainable development.

This article explores the significant role that the state is still expected to play in initiating and implementing the energy transition. In this regard, it is laid out in three parts.

Part I focuses on the premise of the role that derives from constitutional law. This role is considered classic, because it is based on different functions of the state, and the

²⁷ Ademola Oluborode Jegede, *Climate Change: Safeguarding Indigenous Peoples through “Land Sensitive” Adaptation Policy in Africa* in HANDBOOK OF CLIMATE CHANGE ADAPTATION 799-822 (Walter Leal Filho ed., Springer 2015).

²⁸ FELWINE SARR, AFROTOPIA 5 (Drew S. Burk & Sarah Jones-Boardman trans., University of Minnesota Press 2019).

legitimate constrain that distinguishes it from other social actors, including non-state actors. Tremendous materials are offered by the analysis either from the perspective of sociology or law studies when it comes to the specific situation of French-speaking African states. The scope of analysis is broadened with the energy law approach. With a focus on African English-speaking countries, the article examines both the way the state is enforcing statutes aiming to design its own transition scheme and exercising its discretionary power through its energy policy.

Beyond the functions of the state—deriving from its sovereign power—these elements set out the direction in quest of a specific role the state can play in the energy transition as a process in Part II. As such, the energy transition, if it is to lead to coherent social change, requires strong and dynamic leadership, including clear, nuanced, and forward-looking direction on the broad sections of the overall process, and the environmental justice issues that necessarily cluster around them. For this reason, the role of the state is construed as both a steering role, and an integrative role for environmental, economic and social issues. Part III provides a rationale for the necessary and strong support of international cooperation—to the state—in order to achieve the paradigm shift smoothly.

In Part IV, I emphasize the African Union's transition initiatives in the run-up to COP 25, which I hold out as an inducement for states' efforts. In fact, this article seeks to address these issues. Taken together, they could help build a coherent pattern of the role that African states can play in the energy transition.

I. THE ROLE OF THE STATE: AN OLD QUESTION ASKED ANEW

A. A Constitutional Law Rationale

Even in its best state, the state is a “necessary evil.”²⁹ This assumption is most closely associated with the thought of Thomas Paine.³⁰ It reminds us that, at the present stage of the evolution of human societies, the state is the most accomplished form of social entity, but also that it is here to stay. For the moment, it is certainly not going anywhere. Even today, it is the constitutions that determine the design and ends of the state.³¹

From the sociological vantage point, the state is naturally distinct from other organized social groups. The rulers claim and hold—on behalf of the state—the monopoly of legitimate violence³² or coercive power.³³ Here, the regalian missions of the state operate, which suppose the power of sanctioning certain demeanors, certain social behaviors.³⁴ This primary statement is not merely a statement of fact, but a fundamental tenet.³⁵ It highlights the determining role the state has played historically,³⁶ and necessarily continues

²⁹ See THOMAS PAINE, COMMON SENSE 05 (Penguin Books-Great Ideas ed. 1776).

³⁰ *Id.*

³¹ *Id.* at 6.

³² See MAX WEBER, LE SAVANT ET LE POLITIQUE 22-86 (Union Générale d'Éditions ed. 1963).

³³ See FRANCIS FUKUYAMA, THE END OF HISTORY AND THE LAST MAN 16 (The Free Press ed. 1992).

³⁴ See WEBER, *supra* note 1, at 86-87.

³⁵ See 1 LEON DUGUIT, TRAITE DE DROIT CONSTITUTIONNEL 534 (E. de Boccard 3d ed. 1927).

³⁶ See GEORGES VEDEL, MANUEL ELEMENTAIRE DE DROIT CONSTITUTIONNEL 99-103 (Librairie du Recueil Sirey 1st ed. 1949).

to play today in the organization of social relations.³⁷ As a result, any process of social transformation—³⁸which has an impact on the very structure or functioning of the state or its set of values—can only be conceived from the moment when the state really assumes its dominant position in the social order.³⁹ Although, it now has to do so alongside other social actors, especially civil society in general.⁴⁰

Such a position, more than any other, confers on the state the power to enact the rule of law,⁴¹ through the legislative process,⁴² but also to apply it through its administrative⁴³ and jurisdictional powers.⁴⁴

From a purely legal standpoint, functions of the state refer to different modes of exercising public power.⁴⁵ These functions should not be confused with the missions of the

³⁷ See MAX WEBER, *L'ETHIQUE PROTESTANTE ET L'ESPRIT DU CAPITALISME* 140 (1st ed. 1905); Jacques Chevallier, *L'Etat-Nation*, *REV. DE DROIT PUBLIC* 1272, 1272-73 (1980).

³⁸ See EMILE DURKHEIM, *MONTESQUIEU ET ROUSSEAU: PRECURSEURS DE LA SOCIOLOGIE* 115-198 (1st ed. 1918).

³⁹ See RAYMOND CARRE DE MALBERG, *CONTRIBUTION À LA THÉORIE GÉNÉRALE DE L'ÉTAT: SPÉCIALEMENT D'APRÈS LES DONNÉES FOURNIES PAR LE DROIT CONSTITUTIONNEL FRANÇAIS* 11 (Librairie du Recueil Sirey 1st ed., 1920); DAVID ARMSTRONG ET AL., *CIVIL SOCIETY AND INTERNATIONAL GOVERNANCE: THE ROLE OF NON-STATE ACTORS IN THE EU, AFRICA, ASIA AND MIDDLE EAST* 4-8 (Routledge ed. 2015); MARTIN CARNOY, *THE STATE AND POLITICAL THEORY* 7 (Princeton University Press ed. 1984).

⁴⁰ ANDREW HURRELL, *ON GLOBAL ORDER: POWER, VALUES, AND THE CONSTITUTION ON INTERNATIONAL SOCIETY* 6 (Oxford University Press 1st ed. 2008); DAVID LEWIS AND NAZNEEN KANJI, *NON-GOVERNMENTAL ORGANIZATIONS AND DEVELOPMENT* 5 (Routledge ed. 2009).

⁴¹ Boutros Boutros-Ghali, *Le principe d'égalité des Etats et les organisations internationales*, 100 *RCADI* 001, 22 (1960).

⁴² See RAYMOND CARRE DE MALBERG, *supra* note 5, at 285-458.

⁴³ *Id.* at 463-678.

⁴⁴ *Id.* at 691-814.

⁴⁵ *Id.* at 259.

state, the most relevant aspects of which can easily be summarized in a few points.⁴⁶ It is the duty of the state to ensure the security of individuals and the nation against external forces,⁴⁷ to uphold the rule of law and order within territorial borders, to guarantee and achieve the moral and material progress of individuals and the nation, including social, cultural and economic progress.⁴⁸ In order to fulfill these missions, the state uses certain procedures or resorts to certain acts referred to as state functions. For the purposes of this reasoning, we will briefly consider three functions, whose foundations are constitutional in French- and Portuguese-speaking African states, namely the legislative, administrative, and jurisdictional function.⁴⁹

First and foremost, the legislative function is predominant in modern states. In this respect, nothing is more ordinary than the basic mention or constitutional formula according to which:

Parliament shall draft and vote the laws in a sovereign manner (...). Or Parliament shall have power to make laws (...).⁵⁰

Within the domestic legal system, this formula refers to legislative power—namely the capacity to vote the law—which was initially admitted as the “raison d’être” of the parliamentary institution.⁵¹ For this reason, it is undoubtedly

⁴⁶ *Id.* at 263.

⁴⁷ See THOMAS PAINE, *supra* note 1, at 5.

⁴⁸ See RAYMOND CARRE DE MALBERG, *supra* note 5, at 260.

⁴⁹ See 2 LEON DUGUIT, *TRAITÉ DE DROIT CONSTITUTIONNEL* 151 (E. de Boccard 3d ed. 1928).

⁵⁰ *E.g.*, ALGERIA CONST. art. 119, §2; ANGOLA CONST. art. 160, §1 (a); BENIN CONST. art. 79, §2.; BOTSWANA CONST. art. 86.

⁵¹ See RAYMOND CARRE DE MALBERG, *supra* note 5, at 286.

the most significant of the parliamentary functions since it is about making the law on behalf of the people. With due regard to this function, it is asserted that the National Assembly—in most cases—not necessarily the Parliament as a whole—shall express the sovereign will of the people.⁵² By means of the legislative process, the law or statute is regarded as though it expresses the general will.⁵³ Consequently, the deep meaning of this postulate is that laws are derived from the will of people, as it is carried by its representatives in the parliament. That is to say—by its nature and importance—the law is originally an act of sovereignty. It carries out the presumption of embodying the will expressed by the people through their representatives.

The Constitution of Angola sustains it as follows:

The National Assembly shall be a single house representing all Angolans, which shall express the sovereign will of the people and exercise the legislative power of the state.⁵⁴

Once passed by Parliament, statutes become central legal instruments in the domestic legal order.⁵⁵ It should be noted—in this regard—that in most of French-speaking African states, statutes provide authorizations, impose prohibitions, and set abstentions in the actions of individuals, groups or public authorities. Similarly, the judicial review of administrative acts or decisions,⁵⁶ also called contentious of

⁵² *E.g.*, ANGOLA CONST. art. 160, §1 (a).

⁵³ *See* RAYMOND CARRE DE MALBERG, *supra* note 5, at 288.

⁵⁴ *E.g.*, ANGOLA CONST. art. 141, §2.

⁵⁵ *See* EMILE DURKHEIM, *supra* note 7.

⁵⁶ Marguerite Bailly, *L'acte réglementaire illégal et le décret du 28 novembre 1983*, REV. DE DROIT PUBLIC 1513, 1513-14 (1985).

the legality,⁵⁷ which confers on laws the status of a reference norm in relation to other norms such as regulations, reinforces their importance. It is further appropriate to argue that the area of those statutes is generally broad.

By the very nature of things, when a statute is enacted in an area in which the executive branch is supposed to be involved with its regulatory power, the matter becomes purely legislative.⁵⁸ This suggests that a specific procedure will be required for such a statute to be modified or revised by the executive. In other words, the matter must be declassified in the interests of the executive branch.⁵⁹ Accordingly, the procedure will prevent the latter from undergoing legislative amendments, or any kind of standoff, on a matter which comes initially within the purview of its regulatory power, and then will have the ability to amend such a statute.

Overall, there is a variety of statutes which—in addition to ordinary ones—deal with specific matters, including sometimes legislation on strategic directions aiming to define the framework for future legislative action in certain areas,⁶⁰ or programming laws designated to set objectives in other areas.⁶¹ The delimitation of the respective domains of statutes and regulations has made it possible to establish an important borderline between these two domains.⁶² Even

⁵⁷ Yves Petit, *Les circonstances nouvelles dans le contentieux de la légalité des actes administratifs unilatéraux*, *REV. DE DROIT PUBLIC* 1291, 1291-92 (1993).

⁵⁸ Godefroy Moyen, *L'évolution récente de la distinction des domaines de la loi et du règlement en droit congolais* 55 *REV. JUR. ET POL.* 155-164 (2001).

⁵⁹ *Id.*

⁶⁰ Loi d'orientation de l'Éducation nationale of 1991, art. 2; Loi d'orientation sur l'Éducation of 1999, art. 1.

⁶¹ Loi relative à la programmation militaire 2021-2025 of 2020, art. 1.

⁶² See PLACIDE MOUDOUDOU, *DROIT ADMINISTRATIF CONGOLAIS* 22 (Harmattan 1st ed. 2003).

though statutes may set out essential rules in certain matters, they somehow are limited to determining the general principles in those matters. As a matter of fact, the latter might need to be implemented through regulations.

Second, the administrative function is still that of day-to-day management of the state.⁶³ It actually consists of a set of decisions contributing to the daily activity of such entity, including public services, execution of statutes, etc.⁶⁴ Since legislation cannot cover each material case in advance, it is then the responsibility of the administration to deal with ordinary cases and decide.⁶⁵ That is, statutes provide the agents of state with means of action that can simplify their daily activity.⁶⁶ As a result, the area of intervention of the administration is very vast,⁶⁷ since it concerns all decisions that are directly related to the interest of the state.⁶⁸

Regulatory power is a fundamental element of the administrative function.⁶⁹ It is vested in a certain number of administrative authorities,⁷⁰ able to issue provisions of gen-

⁶³ Magloire Ondo, *Le droit administratif français en Afrique francophone: contribution à l'étude de la réception des droits étrangers en droit interne*, 56 *REV. JUR. ET POL.*, 287, 287-333.

⁶⁴ See RAYMOND CARRE DE MALBERG, *supra* note 5, at 463.

⁶⁵ Michel Lascombe, *Le Premier Ministre, clef de voûte des institutions? L'article 49, alinéa 3 et les autres*, *REV. DE DROIT PUBLIC* 105, 105-06 (1981); Pierre le Mire, *La Réforme du pouvoir réglementaire gouvernementale*, *REV. DE DROIT PUBLIC* 1241, 1241-42 (1981).

⁶⁶ See RAYMOND CARRE DE MALBERG, *supra* note 5, at 463.

⁶⁷ Mustapha Khattabi, *Les interventions du pouvoir réglementaire dans le domaine de la loi (la pratique constitutionnelle marocaine)*, 52 *REV. JUR. ET POL.*, 227, 225-233 (1998).

⁶⁸ Jean-Marie Breton, *L'obligation pour l'administration d'exercer son pouvoir réglementaire d'exécution des lois. A propos de quelques décisions récentes du juge administratif*, *REV. DE DROIT PUBLIC* 1749, 1749-50 (1993).

⁶⁹ See RAYMOND CARRE DE MALBERG, *supra* note 5, at 548.

⁷⁰ Tarj Tassou, *La 'chose publique' dans les États africains: sens et contre-sens*, 54 *REV. JUR. ET POL.*, 301, 301-312 (2000).

eral scope by virtue of their power.⁷¹ In some respects, regulatory power operates similarly to the power to make laws, in that the decrees issued have provisions of a general and impersonal nature, which distinguishes them from individual measures taken by the same authorities.⁷² This is a power reserved for the administration, which excludes any legislative intervention. Within this framework, the adopted regulations are considered as autonomous regulations.⁷³ Consequently, the regulatory power cannot be exercised over matters that fall within the legislative power.⁷⁴ In addition to these autonomous regulations, the implementing regulations, which are intended to supplement statutes, contain measures that may implement the general rules laid down by the legislator.⁷⁵

Finally, the jurisdictional function is exercised in the context of the resolution of disputes or litigation regarding facts or legal issues, brought before the various courtrooms. This function therefore consists of applying or interpreting the law in contentious cases on which the judges must rule.⁷⁶ This function has been greatly enhanced in recent developments on the ecological transition by the climate litigation.

In fact, energy law represents an area which applies these general rules deriving from constitutional law.

B. An Energy Law Perspective

The energy transition is rather a matter of energy law. Although most issues that relate to the transition process in-

⁷¹ Mustapha Khattabi, *supra* note 37, at 227.

⁷² *Id.*

⁷³ See PLACIDE MOUDOUDOU, *supra* note 32, at 26.

⁷⁴ *Id.* at 22.

⁷⁵ *Id.* at 26.

⁷⁶ Michel Rousset, *La justice administrative, pièce maîtresse de l'état de droit au Maroc*, 54 REV. JUR. ET POL., 3, 3-14 (2000).

tersect with many other disciplines, energy law and policy fundamentally constitute a necessary means through which the energy transition will translate into law, regulation or policy. With this in mind, this section attempts to focus on the statutory provisions sometimes leading to a variety of design patterns used by some English-speaking states to shape the transition process, while it also seeks to walk through the public policy landscape and reveal some of the policy objectives providing the state with a discretionary power.

1. Statutory Arrangements to Energy Transition

Statutes play a fundamental role in the energy transition, both for the design and implementation of the new energy system.⁷⁷ Besides the classic legislation in the energy sector,⁷⁸ some interesting legislations are spawning transition efforts in this respect. Most of them could be seen as by-products of state commitments to the transition towards decarbonization, but also to ambitious climate goals in some way.⁷⁹

First, it is the primary responsibility of the state to determine the content of the transition process.⁸⁰ This means

⁷⁷ ORTWIN RENN, FRANK ULMER & ANNA DECKERT, *THE ROLE OF PUBLIC PARTICIPATION IN ENERGY TRANSITIONS* 72-74 (Elsevier, Academic Press, 1st ed. 2020).

⁷⁸ See, e.g. Act No 2014-132 of 2014 on Electricity Code in Ivory Coast assented on March 24, 2014.

⁷⁹ Rafael Leal-Arcas, *The Transition Towards Decarbonization: A Legal and Policy Exploration of the European Union*, QUEEN MARY SCHOOL OF LAW LEGAL STUDIES RESEARCH PAPER NO. 222/2016, available at <https://ssrn.com/abstract=2739911> (providing a thorough overview of transition towards decarbonization and underlining EU member states commitments).

⁸⁰ Aubin Nzaou-Kongo, *L'exploitation des hydrocarbures et la protection de l'environnement en République du Congo. Essai sur la complexité de leurs rapports à la lumière du droit international*, 51 (2018) (unpublished Ph.D. Dissertation collection (on file with University of

that rather than laying down general proclamations, or mere promises, laws must set a substantive content to the decarbonization process that in fact can be implemented.⁸¹

In Ghana—for example—the legislator in adopting the Renewable Energy Act in 2011 (hereinafter also referred to as the “2011 Act”) specifies—from the outset—the meaning and significance the country intends to give to its transition effort.⁸² In the preliminary section, the legislature sets out the object of the 2011 Act, which concentrates upon the development, management and use of renewable energy sources to produce heat and power as follows:

1. (1) The object of this Act is to provide for the development, management and utilization of renewable energy sources for the production of heat and power in an efficient and environmentally sustainable manner.

(2) For the purpose of subsection (1), the object shall encompass

(a) the provision of

(i) a framework to support the development and utilization of renewable energy sources; and

(ii) an enabling environment to attract investment in renewable energy sources;

(b) the promotion for the use of renewable energy;

(c) the diversification of supplies to safeguard

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⁸¹ BEHAM MARKUS P., *STATE INTEREST AND THE SOURCES OF INTERNATIONAL LAW. DOCTRINE, MORALITY, AND NON-TREATY LAW* 251 (London: Routledge, 2018).

⁸² The 2011 Renewable Energy Act, assented on December 31st, 2011.

energy security;

(d) improved access to electricity through the use of renewable energy sources;

(e) the building of indigenous capacity in technology for renewable energy sources;

(f) public education on renewable energy production and utilisation; and

(g) the regulation of the production and supply of woodfuel and bio-fuel.⁸³

It follows from this object that such deployment of renewable energy sources must be done in an efficient and environmentally sustainable manner.⁸⁴ Thus, the transition to these sources is strongly encouraged by the law, while ensuring that an environment conducive to such deployment is promoted nationally, including through economic investments that support the sector.⁸⁵ These renewable energies are in fact all forms of energy obtained from non-exhaustible or non-depleting sources, including wind,⁸⁶ solar,⁸⁷ hydro,⁸⁸ biomass,⁸⁹ biofuel,⁹⁰ landfill gas,⁹¹ sewage gas,⁹² geothermal energy,⁹³ ocean energy,⁹⁴ as well as any other source of energy whose status will be determined by the Energy

⁸³ Renewable Energy Act in 2011, section 1.

⁸⁴ *Id.*

⁸⁵ *Id.*

⁸⁶ *Id.* section 2(a).

⁸⁷ *Id.* section 2(b).

⁸⁸ *Id.* section 2(c).

⁸⁹ *Id.* section 2(d).

⁹⁰ *Id.* section 2(e).

⁹¹ *Id.* section 2(f).

⁹² *Id.* section 2(g).

⁹³ *Id.* section 2(h).

⁹⁴ *Id.* section 2(i).

Minister.⁹⁵ This transition effort aims to encourage the development and use of renewable energy within the framework of the consultation platform between the government, the private sector and civil society that will be created by the Energy Commission.⁹⁶ Also, the 2011 Act necessarily emphasizes the diversity of sources needed for energy supply, which would preserve and ensure energy security at the national level. Yet, this objective inevitably involves guaranteeing access to electricity from renewable energies, but also the respective contribution of the traditional grid and the share of renewable energies.

Ghana's Minister of Energy is a key player in this area. His role is broad and includes the design, implementation, and monitoring of the national energy policy, as well as the overall supervision of Ghana's energy sector agencies. In this regard, the Minister of Energy provides the necessary policy direction, on behalf of the government, to achieve the target set by the 2011 Act.

It is therefore up to the state to set out national targets for the use of renewable energy resources. In this regard, a typical example is to be found in Gambia's Renewable Energy Act of 2013 (hereinafter also referred to as the "2013 Act")⁹⁷ which illustrates such a goal. The 2013 Act could be considered realistic because of the targets it sets, which could arguably provide an overview of the new energy mix and allow for monitoring over time. The Gambian Minister of Energy is also a key player in this area, as it is his responsibility to propose medium and long-term national targets for the use of renewable energy resources in electricity genera-

⁹⁵ *Id.* section 2(j).

⁹⁶ *Id.* section 2(b).

⁹⁷ Renewable Energy Act of January 1st, 2013.

tion.⁹⁸ If circumstances require, targets could be proposed on the basis of geographical or social criteria such as diversity. Accordingly, the Gambian Minister of Energy is required to report annually to the Cabinet on these targets.⁹⁹

For the purposes of fostering the transition, the 2013 Act also states that the Ministry determines, on the one hand, the equipment eligible for tax exemption,¹⁰⁰ and carries out, on the other hand, an impact study of the use of biomass for energy needs.¹⁰¹ Among other things, the 2013 Act lays out The Public Utilities Regulatory Authority responsibilities, including the management of the Renewable Energy Fund¹⁰² and formulation of the Feed In Tariff Rules.¹⁰³ Besides, it specifies functions the Responsible Network Utility has when it comes to determine the “safety and technical capability of the grid to connect electricity generated from renewable energy resources (...),” but also whether it will be necessary to develop new grids.¹⁰⁴

Secondly, it is my contention that the state has the sole power to create public bodies, whose purpose is to support the policy direction set by the Government. This is the case of the Mauritius Renewable Energy Agency (“MARENA”) for example. MARENA was created as a body corporate by the Mauritius Renewable Energy Agency Act in 2015 (hereinafter also referred to as the “2015 Act”).¹⁰⁵ Its purpose is to promote the development and use of renewable energy

⁹⁸ *Id.* section 4(1)

⁹⁹ *Id.* section 4(2)

¹⁰⁰ *Id.* section 3(b)

¹⁰¹ *Id.* section 3(c)

¹⁰² *Id.* section 2(a)

¹⁰³ *Id.* section 2(b)

¹⁰⁴ *Id.* section 3 (a)

¹⁰⁵ Mauritius Renewable Energy Agency Act No. 11 of 2015, assented on October 2nd, 2015, and proclaimed on December 26, 2015.

in Mauritius.¹⁰⁶ To realize the scope of MARENA's mission, it must be indicated that the 2015 Act correlates the promotion of renewable energy with the achievement of sustainable development goals.¹⁰⁷ In this sense, in addition to increasing the share of renewable energy in the national energy mix, MARENA will promote partnership, cooperation and networking—at different levels—with various actors in the renewable energy sector.¹⁰⁸ In this capacity, MARENA shall design—every five years—a national renewable energy strategic plan, but also set various instruments of soft law, including guidelines and standards for renewable energy projects, and criteria for evaluation and approval of on-grid and off-grid renewable energy projects.¹⁰⁹

Most of these acts are implemented through various regulations. However, the main tool used by states is now public policies, which give them broad discretionary power and leverage. These policies are either energy and climate policies or sectoral policies, including environmental or natural resources policies.

2. Policy Objectives for Energy Transition

This aspect is intended to amplify the scope of this section, and—for this reason—I will try to provide a very concise overview of the state's role in shaping the transition through energy and climate policy. The spectrum of energy policies is generally always broader than that of laws and regulations. It is further argued that, in light of the separation of powers, policy matters fall under the exclusive competence of the executive branch. Therefore, in order to set policies in areas of energy and climate, the latter exerts a broad discretion.

¹⁰⁶ *Id.*

¹⁰⁷ *Id.* section 4(a).

¹⁰⁸ *Id.* section 4(f).

¹⁰⁹ *Id.* section 5(g).

A brief discussion of energy policy in Tanzania—for example—provides the general context for policy design. The new national energy policy enacted in 2015 provides a history of the energy sector in the national economy, and the general context for the national energy sector, including electricity and oil and gas.¹¹⁰ The policy addresses various issues such as local content, technology availability, financing options, etc.¹¹¹ Its purpose is—inter alia—to facilitate access to modern energy services through the development and expansion of energy infrastructure,¹¹² create favorable conditions in order that energy resources will help to meet domestic energy demand,¹¹³ and encourage the diversification of energy mix through energy alternatives or renewable energies.¹¹⁴ It is also worth noting that the main objective of the national energy policy is:

To provide guidance for sustainable development and utilization of energy resources to ensure optimal benefits to Tanzanians and contribute towards transformation of the national economy.¹¹⁵

Moreover, in pursuit of this objective, the policy lays out broad principles for universal access by Tanzanians to reliable, affordable, safe, efficient and environmentally sound modern energy services.¹¹⁶

Given that, in the first place, it is the scope of the energy policy to reflect the current energy mix of the state, Zim-

¹¹⁰ National Energy Policy of 2015.

¹¹¹ *Id.*

¹¹² *Id.* at 8-9.

¹¹³ *Id.*

¹¹⁴ *Id.*

¹¹⁵ *Id.* at 10.

¹¹⁶ *Id.*

babwe's National Energy Policy 2012, for example, deserves careful consideration.¹¹⁷ It seems correct to mention—at the outset—that Zimbabwe's National Energy Policy is well designed, and its components reflect intelligently the national mix. The policy makes a direct link between energy and development, before providing an overview of the general context in which it is approved, including the state's energy situation and its contribution to the national economy.¹¹⁸ Having this last point in common with Tanzania's energy policy, Zimbabwe's energy policy differs when it comes to the content of the energy mix. The latter clearly determines the respective shares of electricity,¹¹⁹ fossil fuels,¹²⁰ coal,¹²¹ nuclear¹²² and renewable energies.¹²³ As with each sub-sector, the policy considers many relevant aspects, including the social context, policy challenges, objectives, measures, strategies, etc. As a consequence, the Ministry of Energy and Power Development is responsible, on behalf of the Government, to design, monitor performance, and regulate the energy sector.¹²⁴

It should therefore be noted that Zimbabwe's National Energy Policy put forward the gender issues in the energy sector. For this reason, the policy predicates that the role and participation of women in the energy sector still need to be adequately addressed. In fact, some problems are identified in this area, including public or private energy infrastructure provisions that are not considered gender neutral, gender

¹¹⁷ National Energy Policy of 2012.

¹¹⁸ *Id.* at 1-2.

¹¹⁹ *Id.* at 8.

¹²⁰ *Id.* at 14.

¹²¹ *Id.* at 20.

¹²² *Id.* at 32.

¹²³ *Id.* at 22-31.

¹²⁴ *Id.* section 3.

disparities, female-headed households and energy poverty, women's micro-enterprises that are by nature heat intensive but face a lack of energy supply and, especially in rural areas, of support for women who use biomass energy for cooking and heating, etc.¹²⁵

Thus, the energy policy aims to foster goals as follows:

- (1) Ensure that the challenge of gender equality in the energy sector becomes a visible and key concern at the policy level.
- (2) Ensure that all energy interventions create opportunities for women's empowerment and gender equality at the programme level.
- (3) Ensure that space and opportunities are available to women at the organizational level.
- (4) Encourage greater enrolment of women in energy-related disciplines.

In order to understand the adequate application of these measures, it is not enough to be concerned exclusively with the existence of the energy policy or the laws. The role of the state is not limited to the adoption of these instruments and to consider somehow that the transition process is underway. Its role goes beyond the mere adoption of instruments, since it is on the ground of their implementation that it can be effectively verified.

II. TOWARDS AN EFFECTIVE TRANSITION EFFORT?

The state has a tremendous role to play in the governance of the energy transition.¹²⁶ This role must be de-

¹²⁵ *Id.* at 51-53.

¹²⁶ Aubin Nzaou-Kongo, *supra* note 78, at 51.

cisive.¹²⁷ Essentially, this is the mindset which is emerging through the international effort when it comes to transitioning away from fossil fuels. Over time, a key feature of that effort has been to ensure access to reliable, sustainable and modern energy services at an affordable cost. Pursuant to paragraph 8 of the preamble of resolution 71/223—as adopted by the United Nations General Assembly on December 21, 2016—it is the primary responsibility of the state to ensure access to energy services. As a result, a twofold component is deriving from this, including providing impetus and direction, and—in a rather meaningful way—reconciling transition goals with basic social stakes.¹²⁸

A. The Role of Steering the Transition

The state is called upon to play a general steering role. This role stems from its primary responsibility to ensure its own economic, social and—even more— environmental progress.¹²⁹ Therefore, it is incumbent upon the state to design and implement an adequate energy policy, but—above all—to integrate—into its public policies—the necessity to ensure access to reliable, sustainable and modern energy services. Here, the issue of affordability for the public also comes into play, and we will focus on this thereafter. Indeed, the decisive role lies in the direction it provides, ensuring that

¹²⁷ ROSEMARY LYSTER & ADRIAN BRADBROOK, *ENERGY LAW AND THE ENVIRONMENT* 78 (Cambridge University Press, 2006).

¹²⁸ Jonas Ebbesson, *Introduction: dimensions of justice in environmental law*, in *ENVIRONMENTAL LAW AND JUSTICE IN CONTEXT* 2 (Jonas Ebbesson & Phoebe Okowa eds., Cambridge University Press 2009).

¹²⁹ Uma Outka, *Environmental Justice in the Renewable Energy Transition*, 19 J. ENVTL. & SUSTAINABILITY L. 64 (2012); John C. Dernbach, Patricia Salkin & Donald A. Brown, *Sustainability as a Means of Improving Environmental Justice*, 19 J. ENVTL. & SUSTAINABILITY L. 11 (2012).

national development policies and strategies make access to energy a priority objective. In this regard, it is important that the state—at all levels—creates instrumental conditions for achieving its new climate and energy goals, built on traditional pillars of sustainable development.

In essence, African states face a multifaceted role. A key aspect of this role is the capacity of the state to mobilize necessary financial resources to support the transformation of its energy mix. In this sense, it must create and strengthen institutional capacities in a way that better adjust to the transition objective. Without a doubt, this implies that these capacities contribute to set a favorable context to access to more environmentally friendly technologies. This orientation is in fact correlated to the targets of sustainable development objective No. 7, promoted by the General Assembly resolution. 70/1, on September 25, 2015 (“the 2030 Agenda”).¹³⁰ Nourishing the ambitious purpose of carrying the new Development Agenda beyond 2015, this new pillar of sustainable development stresses the importance for states to find crucial financial resources to achieve sustainable development goals (hereinafter “SDGs”).

The resolution not only puts forth a new pattern for development through a set 17 goals and 169 targets—which the United Nations (“UN”) is committed to achieving in full by 2030—it also assigns specific tasks to states. In this regard, many African states are trying to align their regulatory or policy frameworks with SDGs. At the national level—one example that comes immediately in mind is the Republic

¹³⁰ According to its official title: “Transforming our world: The 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development”. This program carries the ambition to eliminate all forms of poverty, achieve sustainable development and promote access to energy for all. One year after this resolution, notably on December 21, 2016, the General Assembly enshrined this goal #7 through its resolution #71/233, with identical wording.

of Congo (“RC”) Strategy for the development of the electric power, water and sanitation sectors. We will focus on this specific policy in order to take a comprehensive view of universal access to energy services. Approved by Decree No. 2010-822 on December 31, 2010 (“the 2010 Decree”), the Strategy for the Development of the Congolese Energy Sectors affirms—from its preamble—the RC’s commitment to comply with the Millennium Development Goals (“MDGs”), as now superseded by SDGs above-mentioned, as well as the decisive role that the state will have to play in the energy sector.¹³¹

Yet—whatever substance might have this conceptual role for African states—it necessarily calls for a threefold observation.

First, comes into play the issue of the existence or lack of adequate infrastructure for the provision of energy services. At first glance, this could be a basic ordeal when considering the possibility of providing access to energy services for all. In some cases, the lack of adequate infrastructure should be a watershed, thus call out for a breakthrough reform. The question then is how to get rid of old energy infrastructure—most specifically—that is out of use. But also, how to reorganize or recycle the existing energy infrastructure, and use it for the new goal of adapting the energy mix. The challenge is indeed not to stagger backwards, but rather to cope with the necessity to identify, set aside and either renovate or change or transform.

The supply of modern and sustainable energy services to all people in some francophone African states tends rather to encourage the development of more appropriate infrastructure and technologies to facilitate people’s access to

¹³¹ Development Strategy for the Electric Power Decr. No. 2010-822 (Dec. 31, 2010).

energy services. Such infrastructure will help increase the share of new and renewable energy in the national energy mix. Also, it will improve the level of energy efficiency and provide the desired energy performance. In addition, such infrastructure could also lead to energy savings. Adversely, from the social standpoint, these various elements raise questions about the means that these states could have at their disposal, in order to rapidly bring about the emergence of sustainable, modern and affordable energy services. Moreover, national policies must be more favorable to this transition, notably through a commitment to establish a more equitable and sustainable system,¹³² to create an environment conducive to investments in the energy system and to encourage public-private partnerships in the energy sector.

A second observation—apparently not unrelated to the previous one—concerns the organization of a climate conducive to the promotion of energy efficiency and the use of new and renewable energies. Such context that would encourage the implementation of public policies to rationalize fossil fuel subsidies, which are considered a source of waste, but also research and development in this area, including tax and customs incentives.¹³³ Moreover, it includes the need to reconcile the orientation towards renewable energies with the rational use of energy in general, through the use of less polluting, low-carbon techniques in the exploitation of fossil resources, as well as the consideration of sustainability in traditional energies. That said, it is also agreed that it would

¹³² JENNIE C. STEPHENS, ELIZABETH J. WILSON, AND TARLA RAI PETERSON, *SMART GRID (R)EVOLUTION: ELECTRIC POWER STRUGGLES* 405 (Cambridge University Press, 2015).

¹³³ Roberta F. Mann, *Delivering Energy Policy in the US: the Role of Taxes*, in *DELIVERING ENERGY LAW AND POLICY IN THE EU AND THE US* 261-262 (Raphael J. Heffron and Gavin F. M. Little, eds., Edinburgh University Press 2016).

be advisable to increase national renewable energy production capacities, the general consequence of which would undoubtedly be the creation of new jobs.

The third observation—which is also of great importance here—regards the adaptation of national legislation to the need to guarantee access to energy services for all. This means—in the first place—integrating this new dynamic of transition into the legal instruments applicable to various fields, including construction, public procurement, electricity, industry, transport, sanitation, etc. In the absence of such an option, recourse to special and transversal legislation is not to be excluded. Also, the long lingering question of a right-to-energy services must be addressed in order to strengthen the legal standing and give materiality to this ambition.

These remarks could also have the advantage of being part of the dynamics of the response to climate change. Therefore, it is also worth mentioning ensuring access for all to energy services, as formulated in the General Assembly resolution 71/233, also includes the need to involve all national actors, and in particular local actors, to better adapt to the ever-roughening realities faced by citizens. This is a very important aspect that could ensure that energy services are more adapted to the needs of public and their cost is sufficiently affordable so that they do not create important social contrasts. In fact, this approach can easily be seen as putting sustainable development into perspective in the context of trade-offs that state is called upon to make.

A proper way to embrace this challenge—it is safe to say—is to spur all actions that respond to justice and fairness. I now turn to the grounds relied on by those who find it decent to advocate for an inclusive transition.

B. The Role of fostering the Energy Justice

The reference to energy transition has tremendously overshadowed the issue of energy justice.¹³⁴ The shift it requires—by its very nature—seems far more likely to rouse close attention than any problems posed by the transition per se. Yet, the energy transition—like any major change—inevitably poses many social, economic, and even environmental problems. It goes without saying that—about most of African states—the lingering question is how undeveloped countries could aspire to and achieve sustainable development? One must assume here the close tie between energy transition and sustainable development.¹³⁵ Africa contributes the least of any continent to climate change, it still has to and will carry a huge climate change burden.¹³⁶ Sub-Saharan Africa—already grappling with the challenge of electrification in different places—has become a climate change hotspot.¹³⁷ As a result, it will inescapably bear the energy transition burden.¹³⁸ Therefore, the matter of energy or environmen-

¹³⁴ JENNIE C. STEPHENS, *DIVERSIFYING POWER: WHY WE NEED ANTI-RACISM, FEMINIST LEADERSHIP ON CLIMATE AND ENERGY*, 24 (Island Press, 2020) (arguing that whether the connections between social justice and climate action is mainstreamed, there should be a de-escalation of hostility toward feminism and antiracism).

¹³⁵ Uma Outka, *supra* note 127, at 64.

¹³⁶ Scott Fields, *Continental Divide: Why Africa's Climate Change Burden is Greater?* 113 *Environmental health perspectives* 8 (2005) A534-7. doi:10.1289/ehp.113-a534 <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC1280367/>

¹³⁷ Dan Shepard, *Global Warming: Severe Consequences for Africa: New Report Projects Greater Temperature Increases*, AFRICA RENEWAL (Dec. 2018-March 2019). <https://www.un.org/africarenewal/magazine/december-2018-march-2019/global-warming-severe-consequences-africa>

¹³⁸ CRAIG SHIELDS, *RENEWABLE ENERGY FACTS AND FANTASIES* 36 (Clean Energy Press, 2010).

tal justice is necessarily an acute problem.¹³⁹ The MDGs—it is safe to say—have not arisen out profound hope when it comes to reducing social inequalities. Neither at a local nor at a global level. Consequently, the immense challenge remains for SGDs to quickly and effectively address the social catastrophe that has been unfolding for over a century.

In some African societies, there is still something of the nature of a plight and predicament. The aristocratic power structure confines a large section of the population, including indigenous people and other social groups, in an awful situation. That is the case of Cameroon, DRC, Gabon, RC, etc. In addition to the fact that most of them belong to the low-income community, people bear a disproportionate share of the economic, social and environmental burden, and is either snatched away or deprived of basic benefits stemming from any social transformation. Thereby, it seems inherent in processes such as the energy transition to cause disproportionate harm to those social groups. The example universal access to energy services is a good starting point in this regard.

Most of French-speaking African states must indeed integrate the universal access to energy services into other socio-economic problems facing them. In fact, the state is called upon to provide direction in these various problems at stake. This is also the premise that emerges from resolution 71/233. It considered the perspective of sustainable development to be the one which offers a framework conducive to the reconciliation of economic, social and environmental disparities. But also, it emphasized that access to energy for all is a core dimension of sustainable development.

With due regard to its role, the state must be able to envisage achieving energy democracy through its environ-

¹³⁹ Uma Outka, *supra* note 127, at 64.

mental policies aiming at ensuring universal access to energy services. The concept of energy democracy means here that energy services should be offered at affordable costs, so that it will reduce both energy and economic poverty and improve the livelihood of people. This seems to align with the vision outlined in the Congolese Strategy for the Development of the Energy Sector.¹⁴⁰ Of course, this apparent link which appears as such, derives from the formulation of the vision by itself, underpinning the vast project it carries by easily suggesting that:

The vision for the development of the sector consists in making available to each Congolese citizen or any user in the urban and rural environment, sustainable energy and drinking water in sufficient quantity and acceptable quality, as well as adequate sanitation services, by making the best use of all available potential.¹⁴¹

As set out in the 2010 Decree, the Strategy for the Development of the Energy Sector clearly pursues the objective of promoting access to energy, drinking water and sanitation services for the largest possible number of people, within the framework of an environmental policy that takes into account all social strata.

After a careful review of the strategy attached to the 2010 Decree, a series of two considerations should be highlighted.

First, it seems clear that the strategy aims to integrate energy issues with social and economic issues, with a view

¹⁴⁰ Aubin Nzaou-Kongo, *supra* note 78, at 51.

¹⁴¹ Development Strategy for the Electric Power Decr. No. 2010-822, *supra* note 129.

to addressing them jointly. A key element of this approach is a constant synergy between access to energy and poverty eradication. Poverty eradication—which is also goal 1 of the 2030 Agenda—is thus referred to as a significant feature of the Congolese national strategy. It is indeed directly linked to the issue of access to energy resources. The strategy emphasizes that guaranteed access to reliable energy services should help eliminate poverty in the long term and then promote significant social integration. Accordingly, it is based primarily on the need to raise the level of access to drinking water from 75 percent in 2011 to 90 percent in 2015 in urban areas. In addition, the strategy emphasizes the importance of addressing this issue within the framework of a healthy and sustainable environment. There is no doubt that such approach tends to reconcile—at least formally—these various challenges facing the state. The Congolese strategy set the need to achieve, within the framework of state incentives, to achieve by 2015.¹⁴²

Such effort is encouraged by resolution 71/233, which promotes energy services as basic services.¹⁴³ The resolution

¹⁴² It is important to note that this objective is far from being achieved at the time this work is being prepared. For the energy sector, specific objectives have been set to raise the rate of access to energy from 60% in 2011 to 90% in 2015 in urban areas, and from 25% in 2011 to 50% in 2015 in rural areas; to ensure that the twelve (12) departmental capitals and eighty-six (86) district capitals are supplied with sustainable electricity. The same applies to the drinking water sector, with a rate of access to drinking water of 75% in 2011 and 90% in 2015 in urban areas, and 50% in 2011 and 75% in 2015 in rural areas; as for sanitation, the challenges are less significant, in particular access to adequate sanitation services in 56% of households in urban areas by 2015. *Stratégie de développement des secteurs de l'énergie électrique, de l'eau et assainissement.*

¹⁴³ Developing countries are particularly targeted here, as the majority of people living on less than \$1.25 a day are located in sub-Sa-

attaches many virtues to guaranteeing access for all to reliable, sustainable and modern energy services at an affordable cost. For this reason, it considers that such a guarantee is conducive to a considerable reduction, if not elimination, of certain phenomena, including poverty, morbidity and mortality, and disaster risks. Thus, the reference to energy services as basic services put forth the concept of human dignity. That is to say, ensuring access to energy is a matter of human dignity, which necessarily changes life quality, but also eases access to health, education, drinking water and sanitation. In fact, with no doubt this challenge concerns both developing and developed countries.

The quest for such synergy will certainly lead the Congolese government to point out social inequalities—in access to energy—between men and women. For sustained periods of time, the national energy policy has not considered the need to ensure access to and deployment of sustainable energy services, while improving gender equality and women's empowerment. The challenge is to raise the level of equal distribution of environmental, social and economic benefits without yielding them to privileged social groups. So, the state must address them—in a cohesive way and more often than not—as a dual challenge of achieving universal access to energy without any gender discrimination—on the one hand—and reducing women's vulnerability due to the lack of reliable energy services, on the other hand. In this sense, the synergy aligns with SDGs Agenda which encourages the state to raise awareness on and develop capacity-building programs on women in energy services. In short, the state must involve women in any national or local actions related

haran Africa or Asia. These people are among the 27 million people who do not have access to clean water and who suffer from famine and malnutrition according to UNICEF.

to the transmission of knowledge and the promotion of access to energy services. Yet, it does not seem incorrect to say that the Congolese strategy did not specifically emphasize the significant element. It merely encourages a global vision of promoting energy democracy without bothering to integrate sometimes relevant dimensions or details.

Yet, one cannot fail to acknowledge that the integration of energy access and food security seems to be a serious challenge. After a relative period of economic fallout, most states in the Central African region, including Cameroon, Central African Republic, Equatorial Guinea, Gabon, and RC, have been struggling to redeem themselves from the financial meltdown underway since 2014. Soon after, they have had to scramble with the ongoing pandemic. The hard fate being almost doubled with a soaring unemployment rate. Then, the government is compelled to take a serious step when it comes to fighting hunger, improving nutrition, and guaranteeing food security. In recent years, some African states faced with food riots have seen them turn into social and political turmoil. That is, food security matters for people in those states. Indeed, universal access to energy must be promoted through a framework, which supports the intensification of agricultural production, by simplifying access to clean production technologies. Whatever the policy content contours could be, it must aim directly at the activity of small producers, including indigenous people, family farmers, livestock breeders, fishermen, and informal economy operators, etc. No doubt, this is a way to arise positive spillovers, create jobs and add real social value.

Second, ensuring universal access to energy services must be addressed in the context of environmental policies. This is a necessary move, given the need to achieve universal access while ensuring the protection of the environment. Its ends are to meet the expectations of 75 percent of Con-

golese people, living mainly in rural areas, who depend on traditional biomass for cooking and heating. Similarly, is it convenient to provide a more appropriate solution to the 40 percent of Congolese people who do not have access to electricity and who, despite the availability of energy distribution services, do not benefit from them either because of the cost, or social exclusion factors.¹⁴⁴

The promotion of renewable energies would thus encompass the expected impact on these social disparities. Improving widespread access to reliable, sustainable and modern energy services at an affordable cost is a social imperative. But if universal access is to be considered “universal,” then its scope must not exclude anyone across the social strata. Such an approach should therefore harbor social acceptance of the process, and necessarily facilitate the advocacy of universal access to energy services. More specifically, to more environmentally friendly energy resources and services. In this regard, one could concur with the idea that promoting environmental protection and access to cleaner energy sources will inevitably spur people’s acceptance. In other words, the perspective of sustainable development would thus be strengthened. This approach could be fundamental for the RC, which is particularly concerned about the need for transition, but is still coping with unsettling social issues, some of which are heart wrenching. This is a double challenge for the RC and any delay in the implementation of the national strategy, which does not address all these social issues, will probably haul other forms of social problems. With no doubt, it requires integrated planning and management of environmental issues and needs as part of the energy and

¹⁴⁴ However, urban areas are not exempt from this dependence, due to customary practices.

ecological strategy.¹⁴⁵

Although this is a real challenge, it must be admitted that it gives the state some leeway in the fight against climate change. Despite the apparent simplicity of such an assumption, universal access to energy would help cultivate resilience and adaptation to climate change as well as mitigation. It could also be said that this is a key element of the UN Secretary General's report on "United Nations Decade of Sustainable Energy for All."¹⁴⁶ The report underlines the urgent need to rethink the global energy system and ensure the provision of quality energy services to provide access to all without discrimination.¹⁴⁷

In addition to reinforcing the Sustainable Energy for All initiative launched by the UN Secretary General in 2011, following the General Assembly's proclamation of 2012 as the International Year of Renewable Energy for All,¹⁴⁸ the report outlines the development of energy access as part of the global strategy to respond to the threat of climate change.¹⁴⁹ As such, the report highlights the scaling up of renewable energy deployment as a key means of doubling the capacity to adapt and build resilience to climate change. This was already reflected in a previous UN Secretary Gen-

¹⁴⁵ In this regard, it clearly emphasizes that "improving energy efficiency, increasing the share of renewable energy and promoting cleaner and more energy-efficient technologies are important elements of sustainable development, and that it is important to promote energy conservation, develop energy-efficient technologies and products, and establish effective mechanisms to ensure a more rational use of energy resources."

¹⁴⁶ U.N. Secretary-General, *United Nations Decade of Sustainable Energy for All: Report of the Secretary-General*, U.N. Doc. A/70/422 (Oct. 14, 2015).

¹⁴⁷ *Id.* at 3.

¹⁴⁸ G.A. Res. 65/151, U.N. Doc. A/RES/65/151 (Dec. 20, 2010).

¹⁴⁹ G.A. Res. 67/215, U.N. Doc. A/RES/67/215 (Dec. 21, 2012); G.A. Res. 70/201, U.N. Doc. A/RES/70/201 (Dec. 22, 2015).

eral's report, "Promotion of new and renewable sources of energy."¹⁵⁰ The latter took stock of the state of the global energy system and considered the broad perspective of a transition focused on three objectives: renewing the global energy mix by significantly increasing the share of renewable energy sources, achieving global energy efficiency and ensuring access to reliable and sustainable energy services for all.¹⁵¹

The General Assembly subsequently endorsed this overall dynamic, emphasizing—for its part—the need to build a modern energy system and ensure access for all to energy services as a means of resilience to climate change. Thus, paragraphs 7 and 9 of resolution 71/233 focused on this issue, encouraging states to show greater ambition and effort in this area and to report, through their nationally determined contributions, on the progressive deployment of new and renewable sources of energy. The General Assembly resolution 70/205 on "Harmony with Nature" had stated similar considerations, making direct reference to the World People's Conference on Climate Change and the Rights of Mother Earth, hosted by the Plurinational State of Bolivia in Cochabamba on April 20-22, 2010.

With the benefit of hindsight, the set of issues we have examined in this section highlights the need for African states to make room in their overall priorities for energy access issues, but also to make sense of the urgency¹⁵² that arises from the need to interrelate energy, environmental and social issues. Consequently, African states must also consider climate

¹⁵⁰ U.N. Secretary-General, Promotion of new and renewable sources of energy: Report of the Secretary-General, U.N. Doc. A/69/323 (Aug. 18, 2014).

¹⁵¹ *Id.*

¹⁵² Aubin Nzaou-Kongo, *supra* note 78, at 51.

change risks compromising—in view of its effects—people’s universal access to energy resources and services. Such risk could create even more vulnerable groups, vulnerable to changes and their effects. The transition process puts the energy system at the forefront, including through the need to modernize it, make it cleaner and safer, and make it particularly resilient to climate change. But it could be flawed if it does not reflect a real social change, especially by relying on the protection of everyone or the vulnerable. Yet, government action can only make a real difference at this time with the indispensable support of international cooperation.

III. ENERGY TRANSITION: BETWEEN INTERNATIONAL COOPERATION AND GLOBAL DYNAMICS

State’s duty to cooperate is a component of the current international peace and security realm. From international environmental to energy cooperation, of course hinged on various means, the sovereign state is a central actor.¹⁵³ Likewise, cooperation is at the heart of ensuring access to energy services. It is both the starting point of the Sustainable Energy for All initiative and an instrumental means for supporting its internal implementation. In this respect, cooperation is expected to take place within the classical framework of the UN and its specialized agencies or related institutions, but it inevitably aims to promote the transition effort over African states and be concentrated on specific issues.

¹⁵³ JOOST PAUWELYN, *CONFLICT OF NORMS IN PUBLIC INTERNATIONAL LAW: HOW WTO LAW RELATES TO OTHER RULES OF INTERNATIONAL LAW* 350 (Cambridge University Press, 2003).

A. A Contribution Within a Global Dynamic

The transition away from fossil fuels is a process. It requires a specific trajectory, a solid set of structural elements, a material implementation, and—most importantly—a diversity of actors. The overall look is about shifting from a perennial exploitation to a diversification of energy sources. Also, it is about diversification of power or leadership, horizontally and vertically.¹⁵⁴ The paradigm shift needed is to be fostered by a global dynamic. It suggests that the transition must also rest on international cooperation, which will necessarily support African states to move gradually—at their own pace—towards their climate targets or transition objectives. International cooperation must be the framework for moving from climate isolationism to energy democracy in the first place.¹⁵⁵ This means that the changing structure of international relations is also at stake in this matter.¹⁵⁶ If energy transition requires a new set of ideas,¹⁵⁷ stemming from a diversity of sciences, including environmental science and engineering,¹⁵⁸ geophysics, hydrology,¹⁵⁹ palaeoclimatol-

¹⁵⁴ JENNIE C. STEPHENS, *supra* note 132, at 51.

¹⁵⁵ *Id.* at 47.

¹⁵⁶ JAMES J. PATTERSON, *REMAKING POLITICAL INSTITUTIONS: CLIMATE CHANGE AND BEYOND* 25 (Cambridge University Press, 2021).

¹⁵⁷ DANNY CHIVERS, *THE NO-NONSENSE GUIDE TO CLIMATE CHANGE: THE SCIENCE, THE SOLUTIONS, THE WAY FORWARD* 11-12 (New Internationalist, 2010).

¹⁵⁸ SYBIL P. PARKER & ROBERT A. CORBITT, *MCGRAW-HILL ENCYCLOPEDIA OF ENVIRONMENTAL SCIENCE AND ENGINEERING* (McGraw-Hill, 3rd ed. 1993)

¹⁵⁹ BRUCE E. JOHANSEN, *THE ENCYCLOPEDIA OF GLOBAL WARNING SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY* 561 (ABC-CLIO, 2013).

ogy,¹⁶⁰ climate science,¹⁶¹ etc., then it is necessary to get it out of the infinite administrative maze, of its impoverishing fragmentation,¹⁶² of any form of monopoly other than truly-science environmental policy.¹⁶³

In this respect, international cooperation is proven to be of great importance. It is a key element of the Declaration on Principles of International Law concerning Friendly Relations and Cooperation among states in accordance with the Charter of the United Nations, which is deemed to set forth international society's constitutional principles.¹⁶⁴ Adopted by the UN General Assembly through resolution 2625 (XXV), the declaration emphasizes the obligation to cooperate in all political, economic, and social areas. As a duty of states, cooperation implies that they must work together based on bona fide motivations.¹⁶⁵ It is also referred to the UN as the framework for the momentum of any coopera-

¹⁶⁰ 3 BRIAN C. BLACK ET AL., *CLIMATE CHANGE: AN ENCYCLOPEDIA OF SCIENCE AND HISTORY* 1118 (ABC-CLIO, 2013).

¹⁶¹ JOSEPH ROMM, *CLIMATE CHANGE: WHAT EVERYONE NEEDS TO KNOW* 1 (Oxford university Press, 2016).

¹⁶² William Boyd, *Climate Change, Fragmentation, and the Challenges of Global Environmental Law: Elements of a Post-Copenhagen Assemblage*, 32 U. PA. J. INT'L L. 457 (2010).

¹⁶³ JAN LAITOS & JULIANA OKULSKI, *WHY ENVIRONMENTAL POLICIES FAIL* 9 (Cambridge University Press, 2017).

¹⁶⁴ VAUGHAN LOWE, *INTERNATIONAL LAW* 90-91 (Oxford Press university, 2007).

¹⁶⁵ U.N. Secretary General, Report on the United Nations Decade of Sustainable Energy for All, submitted in the context of the Programme on the Promotion of New and Renewable Sources of Energy for the Implementation of Agenda 21, the Programme for the Further Implementation of Agenda 21 and the outcomes of the World Summit on Sustainable Development and the United Nations Conference on Sustainable Development. See U.N. Secretary-General, *United Nations Decade of Sustainable Energy for All: Report of the Secretary-General*, § 13, U.N. Doc. A/72/156 (July 17, 2017).

tion dynamic. Yet, when it comes to energy transition, the UN represents, moreover, the framework in which the initiative “Sustainable Energy for All” was launched. One of the ends of that initiative—which has become an international organization—is to harbor the energy democracy.¹⁶⁶

Sustainable Energy for All has been the subject of numerous the General Assembly resolutions and documents.¹⁶⁷ Most of which promote ensuring access to energy for all, doubling the rate of improvement in energy efficiency, and doubling the share of renewable energy in the global energy mix.¹⁶⁸ Over that period, the UN General Assembly advocated that it is incumbent to the state to ensure universal access to energy. Accordingly, the recent resolution 71/233 appears to be the linchpin of this process. For the most part,

¹⁶⁶ *Sustainable Energy for All Statutes*, SEFORALL (Oct. 28, 2016) <https://www.seforall.org/system/files/2019-12/SEforALLStatutes.pdf>

¹⁶⁷ U.N. Secretary-General, *United Nations Decade of Sustainable Energy for All: Report of the Secretary-General*, § 13, U.N. Doc. A/72/156 (July 17, 2017); U.N. Secretary-General, *International Year of Sustainable Energy for All, 2012: Report of the Secretary-General*, U.N. Doc. A/67/314 (Aug. 16, 2012); U.N. Secretary-General, *United Nations Decade of Sustainable Energy for All: Report of the Secretary-General*, U.N. Doc. A/70/422 (Oct. 14, 2015); U.N. Secretary-General, *United Nations Decade of Sustainable Energy for All: Report of the Secretary-General*, U.N. Doc. A/68/309 (Aug. 6, 2013); U.N. Secretary-General, *Sustainable Energy for All: Note by the Secretary-General*, U.N. Doc. A/67/551 (Nov. 2, 2012); U.N. Secretary-General, *Sustainable Energy for All: A Global Action Agenda: Note by the Secretary-General*, U.N. Doc. A/67/175 (Apr. 2012); UNIDO, *UNIDO institutional support for the United Nations Secretary-General’s initiative on sustainable energy for all: Addendum Note by the Secretariat*, Doc. GC.14/18/Add.1 (Nov. 28–Dec.2, 2011); U.N. Secretary-General, *Sustainable Energy for All: Note by the Secretary-General*, U.N. Doc. A/66/645 (Nov. 1, 2011); G.A. Res. 65/151, U.N. Doc. A/RES/65/151 (Dec. 20, 2010).

¹⁶⁸ UNIDO, *UNIDO institutional support for the United Nations Secretary-General’s initiative on sustainable energy for all: Addendum Note by the Secretariat*, § 4, Doc. GC.14/18/Add.1 (Nov. 28–Dec.2, 2011).

it asserted that the UN has a *prima facie* duty when it comes to the global dynamic regarding climate change. The same resolution has framed different elements aiming to foster cooperation within the framework of the United Nations as regards ensuring access to energy services for all. Although the term ‘cooperation’ is not used, it nevertheless structures and shapes the initiative, both in its variations and in the possibilities of deployment of the tools for facilitating such access. Attention is also drawn to the role of ‘cornerstone’ that the UN Secretary General and, through him, the entire World Organization must play. This role is clearly at the forefront of the resolution, when the General Assembly takes note of the report of the Secretary General on the United Nations Decade of Sustainable Energy for All, which it links to the report on the promotion of new and renewable sources of energy, but also calls for the rapid implementation of the Global Action Plan for the Decade.

UN Secretary General is invited in the first place to promote—within the Organization itself—renewable energy, energy efficiency and the adoption of sustainable practices. To this end, policy and measures adopted must be applied in all UN premises around the world. Since such action can only be effective if access to energy services is promoted at the same time, UN Secretary General must reconcile these objectives and support them in all Member States of the Organization. In addition, UN Secretary General should prepare a report on the activities carried out within the framework of the United Nations Decade of Sustainable Energy for All, in consultation with Member States and other interested parties, which should include all related activities carried out and implemented within the United Nations system.¹⁶⁹

¹⁶⁹ This report of the Secretary-General, together with the report

The General Assembly then invited the UN Secretary General to support the new inter-state dynamics resulting from the major challenges facing the planet. As a result, UN Secretary General has been asked to submit two reports in 2014,¹⁷⁰ pursuant to the General Assembly resolution 67/215 (2012) on Promotion of new and renewable sources of energy. In many respects, a review of the two reports clearly reveals that—faced with a planet in transition—it is now more than important to reconcile the issue of new and renewable energies with that of access to these energies for as many people as possible. Moreover, it is a primary duty for UN Secretary General to make global cooperation the driving force for actions that are relayed at the local level. Indeed, the two reports give a clear account of where global multi-stakeholder partnerships are henceforth expected to be in this challenge. In this respect, the supply of energy services—which still concerns many countries—is both a priority and an emergency for the entire planet.

Therefore, UN Secretary General is compelled to mak-

on the implementation of resolution 71/233, is expected at the seventy-second session of the General Assembly, which will include a sub-item entitled “Ensuring access to reliable, sustainable, modern and affordable energy services for all” (item 31) under the item entitled “Sustainable development.”

¹⁷⁰ U.N. Secretary-General, Report on the United Nations Decade of Sustainable Energy for All, submitted in the context of the Programme on the Promotion of New and Renewable Sources of Energy, envisaged for the implementation of Agenda 21, the Programme for the Further Implementation of Agenda 21 and the outcomes of the World Summit on Sustainable Development and the United Nations Conference on Sustainable Development. See U.N. Secretary-General, *United Nations Decade of Sustainable Energy for All: Report of the Secretary-General*, U.N. Doc. A/69/395 (Sept. 22, 2014); U.N. Secretary-General, Promotion of new and renewable sources of energy: Report of the Secretary-General, U.N. Doc. A/69/323 (Aug. 18, 2014).

ing the Sustainable Energy for All initiative a global framework that can underpin actions on the ground, which will have to be financed and technically supported by the established global multi-stakeholder partnerships developed within the UN system. Indeed, it is this framework that must give considerable impetus to the promotion of renewable energy and other relevant initiatives, such as the Global Climate Action Plan. Further, the General Assembly encourages UN Secretary General to carry on his action in this area. Such action will be supported with mobilizes financial resources as well as necessary technical assistance to facilitate access to energy for all. Indeed, it is incumbent upon UN Secretary General to mobilize resources for sustainable energy supply and efficiency improvements, as well as to coordinate and fully utilize the international financial resources gathered for this purpose. These resources should enable the implementation of national and regional projects aimed at ensuring access for all to reliable, sustainable, modern and affordable energy services. UN Secretary General should broaden and increase partnerships and commitments to achieve the actions for the decade and secure new commitments for the achievement of the interim targets by 2024 and beyond. All relevant United Nations agencies are invited to participate in this initiative, so that no state—especially African states—is left behind by such mobilization.

The duty of cooperation enshrined in these various recommendations, in particular in the “Sustainable Energy for All” initiative, is indeed part of an overall dynamic in which traditional cooperation is invited to pin down specific energy challenges, which might require countries to receive help and support from other states and actors. It is therefore a more global, but also more specific, international cooperation that must accompany the action of fossil fueled states, such as RC, towards a more appropriate energy transition.

B. The Specific Situation of Developing Countries

The new choice to be made in favor of alternative energy sources to hydrocarbons is a real challenge, with a two-fold stake: first, the renewal of energy mix with new and renewable energy sources; second, ensuring universal access to energy services. Faced with this double challenge, the situation of African states requires reflection both on the forms of cooperation envisaged and on the specialized cooperation developed in Africa.¹⁷¹

First, it is appropriate to consider institutional cooperation.¹⁷² This is envisaged through the coordination provided by UN Secretary General at the global level and aims mainly at strengthening inter-institutional and intergovernmental dialogue as well as the institutional support indispensable to meet modern energy challenges. In this regard, resolution 71/233 underpins—not without emphasis—the central role that the International Renewable Energy Agency (IRENA) must play in assisting UN Member States to achieve their renewable energy goals.¹⁷³ For this reason, the General As-

¹⁷¹ It is important to emphasize that, in addition to these forms of cooperation, there is national private action. This is still insufficiently implemented in general or in a field such as this. However, local investment could play an important role in reinforcing the bouquet with non-fossil resources and in maintaining employment. Economists are just beginning to study this type of investment, as well as that made by the diaspora to the country. According to recent studies, more than 62 billion CFA francs are sent to Africa and could be directed towards this “green investment”.

¹⁷² Samuele Furfari, *Les agences de maîtrise de l'énergie aux niveaux régional, insulaire et urbain : l'expérience de la Communauté européenne*, 38 LIAISON ENERGIE-FRANCOPHONIE 25, 25 (1998).

¹⁷³ Thus, the General Assembly had approved the work program and budget of this agency (point 2). Here again, it is understood that the General Assembly commits IRENA to continue its activities in the

sembly had expressed its appreciation for IRENA's work to promote and contribute to the widespread adoption of renewable energy and their sustainable use. Encouraged in its energy cooperation activities, IRENA was therefore called upon to mobilize multi-stakeholder partnerships and to promote, both regionally and nationally, the supply of reliable, sustainable and modern energy services at an affordable cost in African states.

Thus, a further concern may arise from the lack of financial resources. This means that financial cooperation must be particularly emphasized. International financial institutions and donor states are invited to support the actions undertaken in the framework of the "Sustainable Energy for All" initiative. Over a long period of time, African states have built up their energy sector with a large share of fossil fuels. The paradigm shift could not be left to private actors alone, but the state must also create a dynamic. Yet, financial cooperation will appear to be of great importance for the state. These initiatives should, *inter alia*, accompany the promotion, encouragement and accessibility of new and renewable sources of energy that are environmentally sound, climate-resilient and low-carbon. However, financing agencies are called upon to finance at reduced rates, adapted to the development structure of each developing country, the energy diversification projects submitted to them. Likewise, such financing must also raise the levels of investment in these countries in order to promote the development, deployment and wider coverage of renewable energy in their territories.

Finally, referring to the reasons set out above, scientific and technical cooperation must represent an appropriate means to transform domestic energy mixes. Fundamental-

framework of energy cooperation, which is one of the reasons for its creation (Art. 4 (B) §4 of IRENA's Statutes).

ly dependent on financial partnerships, this specific aspect should help to develop, disseminate, and transfer—environmentally friendly technologies—to African states by creating conditions conducive to the expected shift. At the outset, it should be noted that this dimension of cooperation seems to highlight the role the Technology Facilitation Mechanism (TFM), created by the Addis Ababa Programme of Action, is going to play in order to support the implementation of SDGs.¹⁷⁴ The goal being in fact to promote SDGs and enhance international cooperation,¹⁷⁵ including multi-stakeholder partnerships, civil society, private sector, scientific community, UN entities and other stakeholders, etc. This cooperation should facilitate capacity building and the provision of technical assistance regarding the deployment of renewable energy.¹⁷⁶

We recognize that both public and private investment have key roles to play in infrastructure financing, including through development banks, development finance institutions and tools and mechanisms such as public-private partnerships, blended finance, which combines concessional public finance with non-concessional private finance and expertise from the public and private sector, special-purpose vehicles, non-recourse project financing, risk mitigation instruments and pooled funding structures. Blended finance instruments including public-private part-

¹⁷⁴ About Addis Ababa Action Agenda of the Third International Conference on Financing for Development (Addis Ababa Action Agenda). GA Res. 69/313, U.N. Doc. A/RES/69/313 (July 27, 2015).

¹⁷⁵ With regard to Transforming our world: the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development. GA Res. 70/1, §70, U.N. Doc. A/RES/70/1 (Sept. 25, 2015).

¹⁷⁶ GA Res. 69/313, *supra* note 160, at § 48.

nerships serve to lower investment-specific risks and incentivize additional private sector finance across key development sectors led by regional, national and subnational government policies and priorities for sustainable development. For harnessing the potential of blended finance instruments for sustainable development, careful consideration should be given to the appropriate structure and use of blended finance instruments. Projects involving blended finance, including public-private partnerships, should share risks and reward fairly, include clear accountability mechanisms and meet social and environmental standards. We will therefore build capacity to enter into public-private partnerships, including with regard to planning, contract negotiation, management, accounting and budgeting for contingent liabilities. We also commit to hold inclusive, open and transparent discussion when developing and adopting guidelines and documentation for the use of public-private partnerships and to build a knowledge base and share lessons learned through regional and global forums.

Broadly, one can consider financial cooperation to increase support to research and development of appropriate technologies, to strengthen governments' actions and the private sector. These efforts will make it possible to introduce a progressive share of innovative technologies. Therefore, the General Assembly encourages financial institutions to continue the actions already undertaken and to take new initiatives to help developing countries and interested parties to plan, finance and implement sustainable energy projects, while ensuring their follow-up and the establishment of national capacities and institutions.

In light of the facts outlined above, the relevance of specialized cooperation on solar energy in Africa, referred to as the World Solar Programme 1996-2005, should be pointed out as a specific framework for cooperation on energy issues.¹⁷⁷ Approved—in conjunction with the Harare Declaration on Solar Energy—at the World Solar Summit held in Harare (Zimbabwe) on 16 and 17 September 1996—the World Solar Programme,¹⁷⁸ following the recommendations of the Rio 92 Earth Summit, aimed at improving the quality of life of populations, particularly in the rural areas of developing countries, through the use of solar energy and other energy sources.¹⁷⁹ Recognized as a contribution to the overall process of sustainable development by resolution 53/7, the World Solar Programme 1996-2005 was considered to ensure the continuity of the United Nations Conference on New and Renewable Sources of Energy initiative, launched in the context of the establishment of a new international economic order. The Programme had placed cooperation in favour of developing countries at the heart of its action, as shown by the numerous resolutions adopted in this regard.¹⁸⁰

¹⁷⁷ Boris Berkovski, *The World Solar Programme*, in ENVIRONMENTAL ENGINEERING AND RENEWABLE ENERGY 151, 151 (Renato Gavasci and Sarantuyaa Zandaryaa, eds., Elsevier Science 1998).

¹⁷⁸ The program was confirmed by the World Solar Commission in June 1997.

¹⁷⁹ Jacques-Césaire Mba-Nze, *Vers une utilisation à grande échelle des énergies renouvelables en Afrique*, 46 LIAISON ÉNERGIE-FRANCOPHONIE 14, 14-5 (2000).

¹⁸⁰ For an understanding of how the United Nations has dealt with energy challenges and the development that this major issue has undergone before the General Assembly, see in this regard the resolutions as follows: GA Res. 45/209, U.N. Doc. A/RES/45/209 (Dec. 21, 1990); GA Res. 45/208, U.N. Doc. A/RES/45/208 (Dec. 21, 1990); GA Res. 43/193, U.N. Doc. A/RES/43/193 (Dec. 20, 1988); GA Res. 43/192, U.N. Doc. A/RES/43/192 (20 December 1988); GA Res.

The General Assembly expressed its satisfaction with the support for the commitments already made by some donor Member States and called on all other UN Member States to contribute to the successful implementation of this program in Africa.¹⁸¹ Therefore, the resolution invited the Secretary General to act in close cooperation with the United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO), the United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP) and other relevant organizations. On the heels of the World Solar Programme, the Programme on Promotion of New and Renewable Sources of Energy would carry on the global effort initiated and implemented 10 years earlier. Resolution 56/200 set the scope of the shift in the programme. As a matter of fact, it comprised 5 major projects, the implementation of which was envisaged only in the framework of international, regional and bilateral cooperation.¹⁸² Afterwards, the necessity for such cooperation was iteratively recalled by 10 resolutions adopted

41/170, U.N. Doc. A/RES/41/170 (Dec. 5, 1986); GA Res. 40/208, U.N. Doc. A/RES/40/208 (Dec. 17, 1985); GA Res. 39/176, U.N. Doc. A/RES/39/176 (Dec. 17, 1984); GA Res. 39/173, U.N. Doc. A/RES/39/173 (Dec. 17, 1984); GA Res. 38/169, U.N. Doc. A/38/169 (Dec. 19, 1983); GA Res. 38/151, U.N. Doc. A/RES/38/151 (Dec. 19, 1983); GA Res. 37/251, U.N. Doc. A/RES/37/251 (Dec. 21, 1982); GA Res. 37/250, U.N. Doc. A/RES/37/250 (Dec. 21, 1982); GA Res. 36/193, U.N. Doc. A/RES/36/193 (Dec. 17, 1981); GA Res. 35/204, U.N. Doc. A/RES/35/204 (Dec. 16, 1980); GA Res. 34/190, U.N. Doc. A/RES/34/190 (Dec. 18, 1979); GA Res. 33/148, U.N. Doc. A/RES/33/148 (Dec. 20, 1978).

¹⁸¹ GA Res. 53/7, U.N. Doc. A/RES/53/7 (Oct. 26, 1998).

¹⁸² These include the renewable energy education and training program, the information and communication network for Africa's renewable energy regions, rural energy production, capacity building and biomass initiatives.

by the General Assembly.¹⁸³ The invitation was particularly valid for South-South cooperation in which some African states, such as Morocco, have already acquired a know-how recognized worldwide. This specificity of African solar energy should not, however, prevent the evolution towards other sources of energy such as wind, which can be of great importance for coastal states, such as the Congo, Angola, Cameroon.¹⁸⁴ Such a broadening of the energy mix can indeed enable those states to adapt to climate change and thus participate in its mitigation.

IV. THE AFRICAN UNION'S EFFORTS TOWARDS THE STATES

The role of the African Union is illustrative of the efforts undertaken by international organizations of this nature to support the action of states in the energy transition process. In this regard, I propose to focus on a few initiatives that are under discussion or that have been proposed by the specialized technical committees (STC)¹⁸⁵ to the Commission of the African Union ("UA").

¹⁸³ GA Res. 69/225, U.N. Doc. A/RES/69/225 (Dec. 19, 2014); GA Res. 67/215, U.N. Doc. A/RES/67/215 (Dec. 21, 2012); GA Res. 66/206, U.N. Doc. A/RES/66/206 (Dec. 22, 2011); GA Res. 64/206, U.N. Doc. A/RES/64/206 (Dec. 21, 2009); GA Res. 62/197, U.N. Doc. A/RES/62/197 (Dec. 19, 2007); GA Res. 60/199, U.N. Doc. A/RES/60/199 (Dec. 22, 2005); GA Res. 58/210, U.N. Doc. A/RES/58/210 (Dec. 23, 2003); GA Res. 55/205, U.N. Doc. A/RES/55/205 (Dec. 20, 2000); GA Res. 54/215, U.N. Doc. A/RES/54/215 (Dec. 22, 1999).

¹⁸⁴ With the prospect of marine wind farms. Bernard Saulnier, *L'homme et l'énergie éolienne*, 35 LIAISON ÉNERGIE-FRANCOPHONIE 4, 4 (1997); Christopher Falvin, *L'énergie éolienne : un vent nouveau qui souffle de plus en plus fort*, 35 LIAISON ÉNERGIE-FRANCOPHONIE 17, 17 (1997).

¹⁸⁵ STC on Transport, Transcontinental and Interregional Infrastructure, Energy, and Tourism.

It is important to note that one of the efforts of the African Union that strengthens the role of the state in the energy transition is the African Union Commission's Initiative on the Harmonized Continental Regulatory Framework for the Electricity Sector.¹⁸⁶ The governance of this initiative, which is still in its infancy, will be entrusted to a steering structure comprising a board of directors composed of five Ministers for Energy,¹⁸⁷ each representing a region of the continent, as well as a technical steering committee led by the heads of the power pools under the Continental Transmission Master Plan.¹⁸⁸

For the implementation of the pilot phase of this initiative, the STC on Trade, Industry and Minerals (STC-TTII-ET) had adopted—during its second ordinary session held in Cairo, Egypt, on April, 16–17, 2019—the “Guidelines for Minimum Energy Performance Standards (MEPS) and Energy Labeling, which will be implemented by Member States.¹⁸⁹ These measures aim to strengthen energy markets at the regional and continental level. However, this effort can only be effectively sustained if support is given to certain

¹⁸⁶ *Strategy for the Development of a Harmonised Regulatory Framework for the Electricity Market in Africa*, AFRICAN UNION (June 18, 2021), https://au.int/sites/default/files/documents/40438-doc-Strategy_HarmonisedRegulatoryFrameworkElectricityMarket.pdf ; *Action Plan for Harmonised Regulatory Framework for the Electricity Market in Africa*, AFRICAN UNION (June 18, 2021), <https://au.int/en/documents/20210618/action-plan-harmonised-regulatory-framework-electricity-market-africa>

¹⁸⁷ Aubin Nzaou-Kongo, *African Union*, 30 YEARBOOK OF INTERNATIONAL ENVIRONMENTAL LAW 8 (2021).

¹⁸⁸ Babatunde Odetayo & Michael Walsh, *A policy perspective for an integrated regional power pool within the Africa Continental Free Trade Area*, 156 ENERGY POLICY (2021).

¹⁸⁹ AUC/STC-TTIET, *Guidelines for Minimum Energy Performance Standards (MEPS), Energy Efficiency, Energy Labeling and Eco-Design at the Continental Level*, AU Doc. IEA24387 (April 14-18, 2019).

countries where access to energy is not assured, and where the need to set up mini-electricity distribution networks in both urban and rural areas is still pressing.¹⁹⁰ It is certain that the contribution of a harmonized electricity market will only be significant to the extent that a number of social justice issues are resolved, such as health, tourism, education and access to information, etc.¹⁹¹

In line with the ambition to improve energy performance, the African Energy Efficiency Program is another African Union initiative,¹⁹² which aims to promote energy transition. Here again, the role of the state is crucial. Its overall objective is to significantly reduce final energy demand and polluting emissions in Africa. In addition to this, the program also aims to ensure broad access to electricity, competitiveness, energy security and economic development.¹⁹³ This program will be supported by the African Energy Sector Transition Initiative, which will initiate and promote “Deep Decarbonization Pathways (DDP)” in regions and selected pilot countries in Africa. Its aim is to provide states with the necessary guidance on transforming their energy systems in the short, medium and long term.¹⁹⁴

Another initiative, which is undoubtedly competing with the first one in terms of the role of the state and public actors, is the African Renewable Energy Initiative (AREI).¹⁹⁵ Its purpose is to support access to energy services and the

¹⁹⁰ Aubin Nzaou-Kongo, *supra* note 185, at 8.

¹⁹¹ *Id.*

¹⁹² *Energy Efficiency*, AFRICAN UNION (2021), <https://au-afrec.org/energyefficiency.php>

¹⁹³ Aubin Nzaou-Kongo, *supra* note 185, at 11.

¹⁹⁴ *Id.* at 12.

¹⁹⁵ *Africa Renewable Energy Initiative*, AFRICAN UNION (Oct. 2016), <http://www.arei.org/wp-content/uploads/2018/09/AREI-Framework.pdf>

migration to low-carbon development by mobilizing public and private investment to finance energy infrastructure. This initiative will concretely facilitate the training of national actors and develop the necessary measures to encourage various initiatives and projects aimed at renewable energies in the Member States. In this sense, the AREI Independent Delivery Unit (IDU) will submit projects to the AREI Board of Directors for adoption and implementation. Similarly, the IDU will be able to promote knowledge sharing in renewable energy research.¹⁹⁶

However, this effort aimed at access to sustainable energy is now conceived only in the framework of the achievement of the United Nations Sustainable Development Goal 7 (SDG7). Thus, the SE4ALL organization is led to work with the African Union to promote universal access to sustainable energy by 2030. In this respect, various actions will be carried out concerning the initiative “electricity for all in Africa,” which will make it possible to release the financing of the electricity projects.

The growing importance of these issues has led the Commission to work on the implementation of a policy framework and guidelines on bioenergy in Africa. In this sense, a bioenergy development strategy and investment plan for the East and Central African regions was adopted by the STC-TTIET. In this regard, the CTS

(...) requested AUDA-NEPAD to assist Member States in mapping bioenergy resources and identifying priority bioenergy projects for development and implementation and to request development partners to provide the necessary support.

¹⁹⁶ Aubin Nzaou-Kongo, *supra* note 185, at 9.

In the same sense, it had encouraged the development of strategies for other regions. Consequently, the Bioenergy Program aims to give materiality to this policy framework. In particular, it aims to build capacity to improve monitoring, reporting and sustainability of bioenergy in the countries of the continent. It will enable states to have the capacity to collect and analyze data on bioenergy and especially to put in place a solid system of continuous monitoring through the implementation of sustainability indicators for bioenergy (GSI). These data will make it possible to know the exact figures of bioenergy production and consumption in Africa.¹⁹⁷

In order to achieve the shift towards more sustainable, reliable and affordable energy systems, the transition process will also benefit from efforts that will be undertaken within the framework of the African Clean Energy Corridor.¹⁹⁸ This is a regional initiative with a dual purpose. On the one hand, to encourage states and stakeholders to develop and move towards clean, indigenous and cost-effective renewable energy; on the other hand, to promote cross-border trade in renewable energy. This effort was initially implemented in the Eastern and Southern African power pool region, notably the Africa Clean Energy Corridor (ACEC) under the IRENA.¹⁹⁹ This effort had been extended to the region of energy pools of West Africa in 2016 under the name of West Africa Clean Energy Corridor (WACEC). In this context, it is expected that the cooperation of states with international organizations, projects of interconnection of energy networks can promote the deployment of renewable energy and that technical and technological knowledge transfers

¹⁹⁷ *Id.* at 11.

¹⁹⁸ *Id.* at 10.

¹⁹⁹ *Id.*

can follow.²⁰⁰

These cooperation efforts to support state action also concern African island states. This is particularly true of the program for the development of solar energy and small hydroelectricity in Africa, which aims to encourage the development of renewable energy in African island states.²⁰¹ This program is initiated within the framework of the African Union Commission to promote the development of solar energy, small hydro and renewable energy in these states that have specific problems and must also participate in the energy transition process. In addition to focusing on the contribution of solar and small hydro in their new energy mix, the program is intended to encourage African island states to gradually reduce their dependence on fossil fuels.²⁰² It is now recognized that these states are facing extreme manifestations of climate change and that the climate risk to which they are exposed is becoming increasingly acute; for this reason, the program envisages placing special emphasis on resilience to these phenomena and encouraging these states to use the renewable energy resources at their disposal. In this way, the Commission will be able to assist African island states to access financing for renewable energy deployment, they can make use of financing obtained through climate efforts or resort to other sources of financing.²⁰³

²⁰⁰ *Id.*

²⁰¹ *Id.* at 7-9.

²⁰² *Id.*

²⁰³ *Id.*